

Assessment of Validity and Reliability of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire among college of education Pre-Service Teachers in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to Assessment of Validity and Reliability of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire among college of education Pre-Service Teachers in Kano State, Nigeria. The study was guided by three objectives and corresponding three research questions. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all NCE II preservice Mathematics teachers in colleges of education, Kano state, Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session; the sample size includes all the population of the study as it is small and accessible which were 221 preservice Mathematics teachers. The PTMIQ undergoes two types of validity: face and construct validity. Establishing face validity, a panel of seven (7) experts was formed, and PTMIQ was administered for data collection to conduct construct validity and reliability. Convergent and discriminant validity were determined for the attainment of construct validity using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The result shows that the PTMIQ face validity index was found to be 86% (0.86). For the EFA each item loaded on its own factor, with no low-loading; all factor loading was greater than 0.50 and no cross-loading. Performing CFA, the Composite reliability (CR) values were between 0.870 and 0.938, and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values were between 0.490 and 0.718, on the other hand, the inter-factor correlation (0.341, -0.135, 0.526, -0.329, 0.372, -0.080) was smaller than the \sqrt{AVE} (0.844, 0.765, 0.847, 0.700), this established convergent and discriminant validity. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.833 using Cronbach's alpha. All the analysis was carried out using SPSS and SPSS AMOS version 26 and 23 respectively. It is found that PTMIQ was valid and reliable that can be used to measure Mathematics identity of pre-service Mathematics teachers in colleges of education.

Keywords: Mathematics Identity, Validity, and Reliability

Introduction

The emergent of twenty-first century have proved the intellectual power of Mathematics is the development of human beings, scientifically, technologically and economically. The overwhelming influence of Mathematics made it possible to stand on its own without relying on any other disciplines, as science, technology, art, and social sciences depend on the subject. This make the subject a strong tool for the attainment of national development goals (Sidi, 2020); this made teaching and learning of Mathematics compulsory in many parts of the world (Gogo et al. 2020)., including Nigeria, at the basic and post basic level (FRN, 2014).

Teaching and learning of Mathematics become indispensable for sustainable Mathematics education in Nigeria and Kano state in particular. This bring forward the need to trained those who will be responsible to teach the subject at basic and post-basic level of education (Jacobs & Durandt, 2017). The minimum requirement for someone to become Mathematics teacher is the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) (FRN, 2014). Such a certificate is awarded by colleges of education, schools of education in polytechnics, and the National Teacher Institute (NTI).

Institutions such as faculties of education across all universities in Nigeria; institutes of education; colleges of education; and schools of education in polytechnics were authorized by Federal Government of Nigeria to give teacher education training in different field of study including Mathematics. Students in such institutions were either in-service or pre-service teachers. In-service teachers were already in the teaching system re-admitted into teacher training institutions or university to enhance their teaching knowledge or obtain additional qualifications, while pre-service teachers are yet to be in

the teaching system (Murtafiah et al. 2018). This research focuses on pre-service teachers in colleges of education offering Mathematics that is NCE Mathematics students.

Pre-service Mathematics teachers in Nigeria are expected to be well-trained in both mathematical and pedagogical content, offering various courses to equip them with necessary knowledge and skills. However, these programs often face challenges in academic achievement, affecting the quality of Mathematics teachers in Nigeria (Ibrahim et al. 2020; Bamidele & Akanmu, 2023). Studies have shown that pre-service teachers are weak in Mathematics knowledge Otun and Olaoye (2019).

The low academic achievement of pre-service Mathematics teachers is alarmingly high. This led to the investigation of factors responsible for the pre-service Mathematics teachers' underachievement. Most of the researchers focused on inadequate curriculum implementation, shortage of Mathematics teacher educators, government policy, and student overcrowding were listed among the factors (Timayi et al., 2020; Jacob & Garba, 2021; Sirajo & Abdullahi, 2023). Furthermore, Mathematics identity is also, factor that can affect pre-service Mathematics teachers' academic achievement but this factor is not well researched (Heffernan et al. 2020), in fact, despite the number of studies conducted on academic achievement, the researcher was unable to lay hands on literature related to Mathematics identity in Nigerian.

Mathematical identity, originally defined as learners' attitudes and beliefs about Mathematics (Gweshe & Brodie, 2019), is a socially produced way of being that is enacted and recognized in relation to Mathematics learning (Darragh & Radovic 2020). Studies have shown that Mathematics identity has significant impact on pre-service Mathematics identity (Gweshe & Brodie, 2019). Pre-service Mathematics teachers' negative identities can lead to poor academic achievement (Kilasi, 2017).

Mathematics identity (MI) is a construct (latent) variable that comprises observed variables. A construct or latent variables, cannot be directly measured unless with observed variables. Observed variables for Mathematics identity include confidence, beliefs, attitude, persistence, self-efficacy, self-esteem, self-perception, mathematical commitment, attitude/interest, motivation, emotions, and experiences of learning Mathematics (Gonzalez et al. 2022). In this study, beliefs, confidence, attitude, and persistence were used to measure the mathematical identity of pre-service Mathematics teachers. These concepts reflect and define the identity of pre-service Mathematics teachers in Mathematics, highlighting the importance of understanding and addressing these constructs in the learning process. Therefore, understanding and addressing Mathematics identity is crucial for the preparation of pre-service Mathematics teachers.

Hence, the need to validate an instrument that can be used in the research of Mathematics identity in Nigeria. This study aims to assess the validity and reliability of an instrument that would measure pre-service Mathematics teachers' identity in Mathematics.

Identity in Mathematics education have invited the attention of Mathematics educator and researchers (Darragh & Radovic, 2020), as strong factor that play crucial role in determining academic achievement especially in the preparation of pre-service Mathematics teachers. This necessitate the development of valid and reliable instrument that can be used for data collection. Hence, this paper sought to assess the validity and reliability of pre-service teachers' Mathematics identity questionnaire (PTMIQ), which would be used to collect data on Mathematics identity.

Objectives of the study

The paper was set to achieve the following objectives, i.e. to establish:

1. The face validity index of the Pre-service teachers Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ).
2. The convergent and discriminant validity of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire.
3. The internal consistency of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire.

Research Questions

1. What is the face validity index of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ)?
2. What is the convergent and discriminant validity coefficient of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?
3. What is the coefficient of the internal consistency of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was used for study. The design suits the study as it allowed collection of data from a large sample size, which is crucial for the assessment of validity and reliability of an instrument. It also, allowed quantitative analysis such as factor analysis and Cronbach alpha computation. The population of the study consists of all NCE II pre-service Mathematics teachers in colleges of education, Kano state, Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session; the sample size

includes all the population of the study as it is small and accessible which were 221 pre-service Mathematics teachers. The Mathematics identity questionnaire was adapted from the work of Kaspersen and Ytterhaug (2020) with a writing permission. Kaspersen and Ytterhaug developed 20 questions, and used the questionnaire on lower secondary students. In this paper, all the items were re-constructed and grouped in to belief, attitude, confidence and persistence as measuring variables of identity. In addition, 34 items were formed in the present study and tested on pre-service Mathematics teachers. The questionnaire was named PTMIQ in the paper. The PTMIQ was divided into two sections, section A contained pre-service Mathematics teachers' personal information such as institution, level, age, combination; section B, contained Mathematics identity items, in this section there are four sub-constructs as observed variable of Mathematics identity. Those are belief, attitude, confidence and persistence. Eight (8) items were formed on each of the sub-construct except persistence which has ten (10) items. Five-point Likert scale was used, ranging from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1) and in the case of negative items, the coding reverse as strongly agree (1) to strongly disagree (5).

The data collected was analyzed using percentage to determined face validity index. A team of seven experts were formed to validate and rate the PTMIQ. The experts include a Professor and Associate Professor from the field of psychology, Measurement and Evaluation, Mathematics education, and Mathematics both from universities. The face validity index (FVI) was computed using Cohen's Kappa index for face validity. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was used to determined construct validity. The suitability of the data set for EFA was examined with KMO and Bartlett's tests. Principal component analysis and the Promax rotation method were used to uncover the Mathematics Identity's factor structures. In the EFA, low-loading and cross-loading are the measures for the convergent and discriminant validity. If the factor loading is below 0.50 this mean that there is no convergent validity, and if the item(s) load on more than one factor, this means that there is no discriminant validity (Hair, 2020). Then, in order to test the accuracy of the EFA structure, CFA was performed based on the maximum likelihood method. The CFA fit values examined were χ^2/df , RMSEA, CFI, and SRMR. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite/Construct Reliability (CR) of the PTMIEQ were computed for convergent validity. For discriminant validity, the square root of AVE was compared with the inter-factor correlation. The analysis was conducted using SPSS 26 and AMOS 23 package tools.

Presentation of Results

These consist of descriptive statistics used to answer research questions; appropriate statistics used for testing hypothesis; Tables should be aligned to APA style; P-value compare with decision threshold – 0.05 significance if necessary. E.g.,

Research Question 1

What is the face validity index of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ)?

The face validity index (FVI) was computed using Cohen's Kappa index, that is percentage. Based on the expert assessment rate, the face validity index (FVI) was computed by $FVI = \frac{SRA}{NR}$ where FVI stand for Face Validity-Index, SRA stand for Sum of Rater's Assessment and NR stand for number of raters. Table 1 show the validators' assessment rates and FVI computation.

Table 1: Validators' rates in percentage and Face Validity Index computation

S/N	Validators	Rates in Percentage	FVI
1	A	94	$FVI = \frac{SRA}{NR} = \frac{596}{7}$
2	B	93	
3	C	83	$FVI = 85.6$
4	D	77	
5	E	83	$\therefore FVI = 86\%$
6	F	85	
7	G	84	
	SAR	596	

Field work

Table 1 shows the validator assessment and the computation of face validity index (FVI). The assessment rates were between 77% to 94% this indicate high rates. In addition, the Table shows that the FVI is found to be 86% which is 0.86 Kappa value.

Research Question 2

What is the convergent and discriminant validity coefficient of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?

To establish the construct validity, convergence and discriminant validity were determined using both Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA).

The suitability of the data for factor analysis was evaluated prior to the EFA using the KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity.

Table 2: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy.

Variables	Values
KMO	0.869
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square 3636.563
	Df 300
	Sig. 0.001

Table 2 shows that the KMO value was found to be 0.869 which indicate the adequacy of the sample. The Table also, revealed Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($x^2 = 3636.563, df = 300, p = .001$) was significant. Meaning the sample size as well as the data is appropriate for factor analysis since the KMO value is greater than 0.60 and the Bartlett's test yields a statistically significant result.

This led to the employment of factorization and rotation methods in order to discover the factor construct, where principal component analysis and Promax rotation are used. This led to the removal of 7 items out of the 32 loaded on more than one factor. Running after removing those items, a four-factor structure was formed as Table 3 shows.

Table 3: Factor Load Values of the Mathematics Identity Construct

Items	Factor			
	1	2	3	4
Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Beliefs (PTMB)				
PTMB_1 I can do Mathematics no matter how difficult it is.		0.762		
PTMB_2 I am a Mathematics person.		0.866		
PTMB_3 I believe in myself as being part of the Mathematics community.		0.789		
PTMB_4 Mathematics learning is not a problem to me.		0.741		
PTMB_5 I choose to study Mathematics by myself.		0.847		
PTMB_6 Our Mathematics teacher sees me as a Mathematics person.		0.849		
PTMB_7 My parents choose Mathematics for me as they believe I can make it.		0.706		
Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Attitude (PTMA)				
PTMA_1 I get involved when someone starts a mathematical discussion	0.880			
PTMA_2 I have good understanding of Mathematics.	0.936			
PTMA_3 I make my own Mathematics problems from what I have learned.	0.896			
PTMA_4 I usually relate what I'm learning to what I already learned.	0.918			
PTMA_5 I learned Mathematics above what is expected in the curriculum.	0.828			
PTMA_6 I attempt to understand why a new formula or algorithm works when I learn it.	0.742			
Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Confidence (PTMC)				
PTMC_1 Learning new mathematical concepts motivates me to expand my knowledge in the course.				0.854
PTMC_2 I confidently solve Mathematics problem without the help of my friends/teachers.				0.888
PTMC_3 I am confident that I can understand Mathematics outside class.				0.884
PTMC_4 I am confident that I could learn Mathematics at degree level.				0.851
PTMC_5 Mathematics does not scare me at all				0.880
Pre-service Teachers' Mathematics Persistence (PTMP)				
PTMP_2 I used alternative strategies when solving a mathematical problem.			0.770	
PTMP_3 I struggle with putting Mathematics problems aside.			0.777	
PTMP_4 When I tried a mathematical method that didn't work, I spent time determining why it didn't work.			0.779	
PTMP_5 I try several approaches to finding a solution and only seek hints if stuck.			0.848	

PTMP_6	If I do not understand what to do, I keep trying.	0.667
PTMP_7	I apply a variety of approaches over time and study previous solution in an attempt to try a new approach.	0.745
PTMP_8	I do not study concepts that I are difficult to learn.	0.604
Eigenvalue		7.809 4.409 2.821 2.030
Explained Variance (%)		31.24 17.64 11.28 8.12
Total Variance Explained (%)		68.28

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

*The Table does not display load values less than .30

Table 3 shows the factor loads and the eigenvalue of the questionnaire items. From the Table, it indicated that there is no cross-loading and no low-loading by having all the factor loads above 0.50 provides that the criterion for an item to be included within a factor is met. Furthermore, the eigenvalue of the four factors together explained 68.28% of the Mathematics identity questionnaire. Hence, it is above the required benchmark of the variance explained which 50%.

By implication, as there is no low-loading it indicate that all the items converge, and no cross-loading means that there is discriminant validity. These findings revealed that all the items and factors were practically significant and feasible to be use for data collection; hence, the construct validity of the items is provided using exploratory factor analysis (EFA).

As stated, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) employing the maximum likelihood method was used to confirm the four-factor structure produced by EFA. Figure 1 shows the factor distributions and values obtained from the CFA.

Figure 1: CFA of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire

Figure shows CFA structure of pre-service teachers Mathematics identity questionnaire. The goodness-of-fit of the structure was summarized in the Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of Goodness-of-Fit for the CFA of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire

Goodness-of-fit Indices	Acceptable Level of Fit	Fit Values Found
χ^2/df or CIMIN/DF	≤ 3.5 to 0 (perfect fit) and ($P < 0.05$)	2.211
Root Mean Residual (RMR)	Close to 0 (perfect fit)	0.037
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	Value should be equal to or greater than 0.90	0.908
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	Value should be equal to or greater than 0.90	0.907
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	Value below 0.08 indicates very good fit.	0.078
Standard Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	Value should be equal to or less than 0.08	0.055

Table 4. shows the summary of goodness-of-fit CFA model. The Table indicate that the model has a good fit. All the goodness-of-fit measures met their respective acceptable criteria. This indicates that the proposed model fits the data reasonably well. A good fit of the CFA model led to the computation of convergent and discriminant validity. As a consequence of the CFA, the standardized regression weights and correlation values in the AMOS output were used to compute the convergent and discriminant validity. The computation was done in Excel validity calculator, developed by Johnson. The composite/construct reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) provide the convergent validity if the CR values are greater or equal to 0.70 and the AVE values are greater or equal to 0.50. For discriminant validity, the square root of the AVE (\sqrt{AVE}) value is compared with the inter-factor correlation. If the inter-factor correlation is smaller than the \sqrt{AVE} then discriminant validity is achieved. Table 4 provides the CR, AVE, \sqrt{AVE} , and inter-factor correlation values for the convergent and discriminant validity of the Mathematics identity items.

Table 4: CR, AVE, Square root of AVE and Inter-Factor Correlation Values

Variables	CR	AVE	PTMC	PTMB	PTMA	PTMP
PTMC	0.925	0.713	0.844			
PTMB	0.907	0.585	0.341	0.765		
PTMA	0.938	0.718	-0.135	-0.329	0.847	
PTMP	0.870	0.490	0.526	0.372	-0.080	0.700

From Table 4, all the CR values of the factors were greater than .70 and the AVE values were also greater than .50 except that of PTMP, which is 0.49, and it is accepted since the CR value of the PTMP is greater than 0.70 (Sujati et al. 2020). This provides the convergent validity for Mathematics identity. On the other hand, the inter-factor correlation of the variables (0.341, -0.135, 0.526, -0.329, 0.327, -0.080) was smaller than the square root of the AVE (0.844, 0.765, 0.847, 0.700) revealing discriminant validity exist. This meaning that all the items were in the same direction toward measuring Mathematics identity. Hence, the construct validity of the Mathematics identity scale is achieved.

Research Question 3

What is the coefficient of the internal consistency of Mathematics Identity Questionnaire?

Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient was computed for the pre-service teachers Mathematics identity questionnaire as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Cronbach Alpha Coefficient of the Mathematics Identity Questionnaire.

S/N	Factors	No. of Items	Cronbach Alpha
1	PTMC	5	0.928
2	PTMB	7	0.907
3	PTMA	6	0.936
4	PTMP	7	0.866
Mathematics Identity Total Items		25	0.833

Table 5 shows the Cronbach alpha coefficient gained for the each of the factors of the questionnaire, The Cronbach alpha coefficient gained for the questionnaire is found to be 0.833. This alpha value confirmed that of the CR values, and are all above 0.70 which is the minimum acceptable value of reliability.

Summary of Findings

1. The PTMIQ has high index of face validity as the FVI = 0.86, that it appears to measure what it is supposed to measure.
2. The construct validity of the PTMIQ is achieved, as it met all the requirement in both EFA and CFA. That is, no cross-loading and no low-loading, and all the factor loads were above 0.50 in EFA. Also, composite reliability and average variance extraction are above 0.7 and 0.5 respectively in CFA.
3. The PTMIQ is reliable as the Cronbach alpha is found to be 0.83.

Discussion of findings

This study was set to provide a scientifically validated and reliable instrument that contributes to understanding and improving Mathematics teacher education. Therefore, the main goal of the study was to validate the adapted Pre-Service

Teachers' Mathematics Identity Questionnaire (PTMIQ). The PTMIQ was adapted and went through validation processes to ensure its reliability and validity. Validation procedures included face and construct validity assessments. For construct validity and reliability, the instrument was administered on 221 pre-service Mathematics teachers, with five PTMIQ rejected due to errors in completion. Where three having missing values, which was addressed using the "mean of nearby points" method in the SPSS package. The face validity index (FVI) was found to be 0.86 or 86% indicating that it is within the acceptable range, this finding is in line with Roy et al. (2023). However, the questionnaire was adapted from original sources without face validity assessments and were not grouped in to sub-constructs.

The study found that the construct validity was achieved through both EFA and CFA. The finding is in line with the finding of the original sources original of the items, Kaspersen and Ytterhaug (2020) who carryout content, substantive, generalizability, and structural validity. The researchers also obtained a reliability coefficient of 0.86 using Cronbach alpha which is similar to the reliability found in this study.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it is concluded that the pre-service teachers Mathematics identity questionnaire is valid and reliable. Hence, it can be used to collect data on Mathematics identity on pre-service Mathematics teachers.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended to use PTMIQ for data collection as a valid and reliable instrument for measuring pre-service teachers' mathematics identity.
2. Mathematics departments in colleges of education are recommended to utilize the PTMIQ to assess pre-service teachers' mathematics identity during admission.
3. It is recommended to apply this validated instrument to broader contexts, such as assessing pre-service Mathematics teachers' Mathematics identity across educational institutions or regions, to gather more comprehensive data for comparative analysis.

Acknowledgments

The researchers thank to Kaspersen, E. & Ytterhaug, B.O. (2020) for granting permission to adapt their instrument, which become the basis of developing the PTMIQ. Furthermore, pre-service Mathematics teachers will not be left, for their time to fill the questionnaire. The Mathematics departments of the colleges also, were acknowledge for the opportunity given to carry out the study.

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